

PATTERN

Next-generation ultra-high-speed microwave
Photonic integrATed circuiTs using **advancEd**
hybRid iNtegration

The PATTERN project will develop the world's first Process and Assembly Design Kits (PDK & ADK) for microwave photonics at ultra-high frequencies (100+ GHz) as well as new methods of heterogeneous integration of III-V gain materials (e.g. InP) and BiCMOS drivers with electro-optic and nonlinear platforms such as lithium niobate on insulator (LNOI). The project envisions to:

DESIGN

novel advanced PIC building blocks such as **acousto-optic modulators (AOMs)** by combining surface acoustic waveguides (SAWs) and waveguides as well as **magneto-optic isolators** through hybrid integration of yttrium iron garnet (YIG) and LNOI

DEVELOP

a wafer-scale solution for **heterogeneous integration** of indium phosphite (InP) **gain chips and photodetectors on top of an LNOI platform** by means such as **flip-chip bonding and micro-transfer print**

COVER

all processing steps and expertise for **microwave photonics at ultra-high speeds** (above 100 GHz), from PDK components such as **LNOI modulators** and **InP detectors** to assembly and **packaging** as well as **BiCMOS drivers** and **design software** for microwave photonics

ENABLE

unrivalled new PIC functionalities, components and subsystems such as **fast tuneable lasers** for a vast range of applications, from quantum computing and quantum communication to ultra-high-speed telecom, optical computing, sensing and metrology

DEMONSTRATE

the capabilities of the new ultra-high-speed components and heterogeneous integration through **six major prototypes** for different end-user applications in the fields of **quantum computing** and **sensing** to **space communication systems** and **low-noise microwave generation (OEOs and OPLLs)**

THE PROJECT

PROJECT ACRONYM & TITLE PATTERN Next-generation ultra-high-speed microwave Photonic integrATed circuiTs using advancEd hybRid iNtegration		STARTING DATE 01/09/2022 DURATION 48 months
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10 partners	6 European countries	
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